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Ensuring Food Security in Russia: Current State of Affairs, Challenges, and Opportunities for Development

KEYWORDS

national security,
economic
security,
food security,
food security
doctrine,
agro-industrial
complex,
agriculture,
public policy

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of this study lies in the imperative to ensure a sustainable food supply for Russia amid both global and domestic challenges, to reduce dependence on imports, to develop the agricultural sector, and to leverage innovation to strengthen the country's food security and sovereignty.

This article aims to analyze the current state of food security in Russia, to identify existing challenges, and to explore strategies for its improvement and sustainable development.

Materials and methods. The study utilized articles from scientific journals and conference proceedings, as well as official statistics from the Federal State Statistics Service and the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation. The analysis relied on data concerning Russia's food supply from 2015 to 2024 and on the prevalence of food insecurity among the population.

Results. Food security in Russia is characterized by generally favorable indicators across most major products, including grain, oil, potatoes, meat, fish, and eggs. However, some products (milk, vegetables, fruits, and salt) fall below recommended thresholds and are particularly crucial for vulnerable populations. Key internal challenges include high public debt, a decline in small-scale farms, and dependence on energy resources and quality standards. External threats include economic sanctions, currency fluctuations, and volatility in energy prices. Despite a decrease in acute food insecurity, access to adequate food remains constrained by financial difficulties and high inflation, especially among people living in poverty.

Conclusion. A comprehensive state food security strategy should ensure both the availability and quality of food products, support innovation in production, strengthen the integration of production, processing, and distribution chains, and reduce reliance on imports while promoting exports. Achieving these goals requires implementing national projects, optimizing logistics, establishing healthy eating standards, and continued support for innovation within the food industry.

FOR CITATION

Received: Jun 13, 2025
Accepted: Sep 8, 2025
Published: Dec 1, 2025

Ibragimov, A. G., & Antonescu, D. (2025). Ensuring Food Security in Russia: Current State of Affairs, Challenges, and Opportunities for Development. *Economic Consultant*, (4), 55–71. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2025.4.4>

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INTRODUCTION

In the international arena, the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), established in 1945, plays a central role in promoting food security. It assists countries in developing their agricultural sectors and reducing reliance on food imports. According to the FAO, a country is considered food secure if it can satisfy at least 70% of its food needs through domestic production. This level of self-sufficiency ensures the saturation of the domestic market and reduces dependence on external supplies. Achieving this objective requires ensuring safety at every stage of the food chain, from production to consumption. It is essential to distribute products efficiently, maintain their safety, and optimize stock levels, particularly for goods with limited shelf life [1].

National security encompasses the protection of citizens' interests, well-being, independence, and the inviolability of the state's territory. It spans multiple domains, including defense, public and state security, information technology, environmental protection, the economy, transport, energy, and the personal rights of citizens. Economic security is particularly crucial, as it forms the foundation of statehood. Sustainable economic development not only meets societal needs but also safeguards national interests from both internal and external threats. A key component of economic security is food security, defined as the country's ability to independently produce sufficient food and guarantee its availability to all citizens in accordance with rational consumption standards.

The relevance of studying food security in Russia arises from global risks and challenges, including sanctions, climate change, economic instability, and trade conflicts. Food security is a critical national priority that ensures the country's stability, sovereignty, and socio-economic development. Ensuring adequate food supply, promoting income growth, and reducing social inequality are essential objectives of national food policy.

This article aims to examine the current state of food security in Russia, identify the main challenges, and outline promising strategies and directions for its improvement and sustainable development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials consisted of articles published in peer-reviewed scientific journals, including *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, *Vegetable*

Crops of Russia, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Regional Environmental Change, and Eurasian Geography and Economics, as well as abstracts from international conferences such as *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, MATEC Web of Conferences, BIO Web of Conferences, E3S Web of Conferences*, and others.

Data from the official statistics of the Federal State Statistics Service and the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation were also utilized. In particular, the analysis focused on Russia's self-sufficiency in food production for the period 2015-2024, as well as on the prevalence of moderate and acute food insecurity among the population.

LITERARY REVIEW

Currently, Russia maintains a high level of food security due to the development of the agricultural sector, stable production of key products, and export potential. However, challenges related to logistics, sanctions, and climatic conditions persist, requiring further measures to achieve sustainability.

I. Boldyreva et al. note that food security, as an integral component of a state's economic security, is one of the central concerns of monetary policy in most post-Soviet countries. According to the authors, while the initial task of governments in the early stages of market reforms in the former USSR was to fill domestic food markets regardless of the import component, today food sovereignty, including both the availability and quality of food, has come to the fore [2].

S. K. Wegren et al. argue that the traditional interpretation of "food security" refers primarily to the availability and nutritional value of food. According to this conventional definition, the vast majority of the Russian population does not experience food shortages. Nevertheless, the Russian political leadership asserts that Russia faces food shortages due to reliance on imports [3].

I. V. Romanova et al. emphasize that ensuring food security is not solely focused on the productive activities of organizations and agro-industrial complexes, but primarily on improving the living standards of the population and enhancing the overall well-being of the Russian economy. The authors examine the principal risks and threats, internal factors affecting national food security, and outline key aspects of state support for agriculture that ensure the food independence of the Russian Federation [4].

E. N. Antamoshkina and A. F. Rogachev argue that the economic accessibility of food determines the population's ability to purchase it, depending on income levels and price dynamics. Their calculations indicate that a comprehensive assessment of food security in Russia scores 8 points, which corresponds to the permissible level. At the same time, explicit threats persist, including relatively high income inequality in the regions and a rising food price index [5].

I. G. Ushachev et al. note that since 2014, when an active import-substitution policy was initiated, significant changes have occurred in Russia's foreign trade in agricultural products and food, characterized by a reduction in imports and an increase in exports. However, demand for farm products remains constrained by declining incomes and pronounced income inequality. The authors stress the importance of ensuring that the objectives set for the agro-industrial complex are met to achieve national food security, increase the export potential of domestic agri-food products, and implement the planned measures, including the allocation of necessary financial resources [6].

A. Yu. Mokhov analyzes the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic and the impact of sanctions imposed on the Russian Federation by individual states and international organizations. In the context of these sanctions, the intensification of the national agro-industrial complex is highlighted, particularly through increasing domestic agricultural output and protecting citizens' rights in the area of nutrition [7].

M. V. Petrova et al. examine and assess Russia's food security, evaluating the country's potential to enhance food security and expand exports of agricultural products and food [8].

E. Karanina et al. conducted an analysis of food security in Russia in terms of independence, economic accessibility, and physical accessibility of food. According to their findings, the current import-substitution program has proven effective, as there are no viable alternative development paths. An essential factor in this context is the slow pace of development in Russia's domestic economy, coupled with an almost complete lack of competition in domestic markets [9].

I. N. Safiullin et al. assess the food security of the Russian Federation. The researchers conclude that the current structure of consumption does not meet scientifically based dietary standards. For essential food categories such as fruits, milk, and vegetables, the required levels of consumption are not achieved. Furthermore, the

Russian population spends less than one-third of its income on food, indicating an average level of food provision [10].

V. D. Goncharov et al. examine the primary challenges in ensuring food security in the Russian Federation. Their analysis focuses on the existing material and technical base of agriculture, the regional distribution and specialization of agricultural production, energy efficiency, and import substitution [11].

M. Y. Ksenofontov et al. review existing approaches to defining food security. The authors trace the evolution of the concept within the context of the country's socio-economic development and substantiate the current directions for its adaptation in the Russian Federation [12].

Y. S. Pappe et al. conclude that there are no significant threats to the Russian market from the global food market. The researchers also propose alternative definitions and classifications of the agri-food system [13].

The main challenges in ensuring food security in Russia include high levels of income and price inequality, insufficient internal competition, underdeveloped agriculture, dependence on imports of certain products, and socio-economic difficulties related to rising prices and the population's income levels.

R. Mukhametzyanov et al. argue that despite the strengthening of import-substitution measures after 2014, complete self-sufficiency in all food categories has not yet been achieved. This is due to objective constraints in the production of vegetables and fruits and insufficient efforts to develop key sectors such as dairy and beef cattle breeding. Their analysis of the capacity and structure of the Russian food market indicates that, in the long term, the population's consumption patterns remain imbalanced due to low incomes. Moreover, the reduction in disposable income over the past six years has shifted consumption toward cheaper, lower-quality products [14].

M. Y. Ksenofontov et al. also address the methodological challenges in defining regional food security, highlighting the risks of overextending the concept to include conditions for regional food self-sufficiency. The authors emphasize the need to coordinate regional agricultural development programs at the federal level [15].

V. A. Tikhomirova notes that the implementation of the Food Security Doctrine has helped overcome systemic problems in the domestic agro-industrial complex and increase the sustainable production of key crops and aquatic biological resources. However, the situation in animal husbandry is less favorable: while import substitution

in poultry and pork has been successful, resource-intensive sectors such as cattle production and dairy farming remain stagnant [16].

According to J. V. Gnezdova et al., logistics is one of the main factors in modernizing agricultural production and the agro-industrial complex. The researchers note that by 2016 the fleet of fixed assets had decreased significantly: tractors by 12 times, grain harvesters by 11 times, flax harvesters by 103 times, forage harvesters by 9 times, and milking parlors by 9 times, amounting to an overall reduction of 14 times [17].

Specific proposals for ensuring food security in Russia include the development of domestic agriculture and support for farmers, implementation of import-substitution programs, adoption of technologies to increase yields, and related measures.

M. N. Kabanenko and S. N. Ugrimova argue that the development of the agricultural sector is a priority for addressing food security challenges. They highlight the importance of international food trade and the state's foreign policy in this domain. Thus, the combination of production and trade development represents an effective strategy for ensuring national food security [18].

O. V. Kirillova et al. emphasize that the innovative development of the Russian agro-industrial complex and the achievement of national food security require: the creation of a research and development sector in food production; reform of the education system to support innovation in the agro-industrial complex; technical re-equipment of agricultural enterprises; establishment of agricultural consulting services for producers; creation of systems for protecting intellectual property; improvement of legal regulation concerning innovation, research, and development; and attention to the specific needs of agriculture and agribusiness [19].

M. A. Ananiev et al. identify the main challenges and threats to food security, including low real incomes, a limited share of highly processed products in exports, the ongoing effects of Western sanctions, and the low technological and innovative development of the agro-industrial complex. To address these issues, the researchers propose measures such as increasing the economic and physical accessibility of food, developing the production and scientific-technical potential of the agro-industrial complex, amending the Food Security Doctrine, introducing innovative technologies in crop production, and improving production efficiency [20].

I. Baranova et al. propose measures to strengthen Russia's food security, taking into account the unpredictable development of the national economy. They conclude that, despite existing challenges, the Russian agro-industrial complex

continues to provide food for the population effectively and maintains momentum in expanding exports [21].

V. Chigvintsev et al. identify food-related risks and threats to national security and propose the most effective agrarian policy model for modern Russia. Their findings indicate that state protectionism is a priority within agricultural policy for ensuring economic and national security [22].

O. T. Ergunova et al. suggest the use of new technologies and innovative approaches to market participation to promote import substitution and increase the efficiency of regional agro-industrial complexes in the Russian Federation. The authors also outline the prerequisites for the formation and development of a "smart developed economy" in the context of the marine agri-food revolution 4.0 [23].

G. V. Fedotova et al. evaluate the quality of transformations in the structure of the national economy in light of the transition to Industry 4.0. They focus on forecasts of potential reductions in food production, assess the scope of digitalization in the agro-industrial complex, and provide recommendations for transitioning to the Agriculture 4.0 paradigm under contemporary conditions [24].

Agriculture remains the foundation of food security in Russia, as it ensures domestic food production, reduces dependence on imports, creates employment opportunities, and maintains stability in the country's food supply.

A. V. Soldatenko et al. analyzed indicators of sown area, gross harvest, and yield across the administrative districts of the Russian Federation. The authors identified the leading federal subjects based on these indicators and concluded that the domestic market has high capacity. They also proposed strategies to increase production in the vegetable-growing sector. The most critical factors limiting the production of high-quality, competitive vegetable products were identified, and recommendations for addressing them were provided [25].

N. Dronin and A. Kirilenko examined the impact of climate change on grain production in Russia. They found that the commonly held perception of beneficial effects from a warmer climate is unlikely to hold, primarily due to the increased risk of drought in the country's most important agricultural regions. The authors also analyzed adaptation strategies to mitigate the growing risks of crop failure [26].

A. E. Suglobov and A. V. Rodionov studied leading production indicators for certain feed crops. They identified trends in milk production and herd size, and quantified the volume of imports of milk substitutes, particularly those based on palm oil [27].

According to A. L. Zolkin et al., grain production constitutes one of the most essential foundations of crop production and, more broadly, all agricultural output. The authors argue that modern agrarian policy in Russia should be comprehensive, well-funded, and based on a stable legislative framework, while also accounting for significant regional differences in levels of agricultural development [28].

R. Kh. Adukov and A. N. Adukova note that in Russia, food security relies heavily on extensive agricultural holdings, which can impede the balanced development of all forms of farm management. They advocate for strengthening the social orientation of agrarian policy and prioritizing regional food self-sufficiency [29].

N. Shagaida et al. provide insights from expert interviews with small-scale agricultural producers, highlighting additional opportunities that emerged during the period of the food embargo [30].

In summary, food security is a critical component of Russia's economic security. Most researchers identify internal risks, including income inequality, price volatility, and underdeveloped domestic markets, alongside the ongoing effects of import-substitution measures initiated since 2014. Overall, Russia's food security is assessed as acceptable, but social and economic factors pose continuing threats. The literature emphasizes the importance of developing the agricultural sector to ensure food security, recommending measures such as enhancing innovation, technical modernization, scientific research, legal regulation, and support for agribusiness. Major threats include low incomes, sanctions, and insufficient levels of processing and technological development.

RESULTS

In the context of ensuring food security in the Russian Federation, two key aspects can be distinguished that have a significant impact on the situation [31]:

1. External factors affecting the food security of the Russian Federation:
 - economic restrictions and trade conflicts;
 - insufficient competitiveness of Russian agricultural products in the international arena;
 - instability of the national currency;
 - fluctuations in energy prices.

2. Domestic factors threatening the country's food security:

- high levels of household debt combined with low incomes;
- reduced number of small farms, and production concentrated in large companies;
- tightening product quality standards and changing consumption patterns;
- insufficient development of agricultural infrastructure and dependence on energy costs.

To ensure food security, it is necessary to protect the domestic market and provide support to large producers, farmers, and personal subsidiary plots.

Russia possesses significant agricultural resources comparable to those of China and Indonesia. The imposition of sanctions has reduced imports, thereby stimulating domestic production.

According to the Russian Ministry of Agriculture, in 2024, food security indicators were exceeded for several key products: grain – 149%, vegetable oil – 252%, potatoes – 101%, sugar – 107%, meat – 102%, fish – 152.9%, and eggs – 98.6%. However, some products remain below threshold values: milk – 86%, vegetables and melons – 89.4%, fruits and berries – 46.7%, and table salt – 68.5% (see Table 1 and Fig. 1) [32].

Table 1

Provision of Russia with Domestically Produced Food, 2015-2024, (%)

	2015	2020	2024	In 2024, compared to 2020	Threshold value
Grain	160	149.1	149	-0.1	95
Vegetable oil	142.6	125.5	252	+126.5	90
Sugar	105.9	100.6	107	+6.4	90
Potatoes	93.2	102.1	101	-1.1	95
Milk and milk products	80.7	79.9	86	+6.1	90
Meat and meat products	90.6	88.7	102	+13.3	85
Fish	132.8	160.7	152.9	-7.8	85
Egg	98.2	97.4	98.6	+1.2	98.6
Vegetables and melons	87.4	86.8	89.4	+2.6	90
Fruits and berries	36.5	32.5	46.7	+14.2	60
Table salt	68.5	65.7	68.5	+2.8	85

Figure 1 Dynamics of Russia's Food Supply from Domestic Production in 2024 Compared to 2020, (%)

Among all foods that remain below target levels, milk is particularly important for the nutrition of vulnerable populations, including children and the elderly. According to Russia's food security strategy, the share of domestically produced milk and dairy products should reach at least 90% of the population's needs. In this context, Russian producers face the challenge of increasing milk production by 6-7 million tons in the shortest possible time [33].

Significant changes have also occurred in the production of vegetable oils. In 2024, sunflower oil production rose to 8 million tons, while soybean oil production reached 1.1 million tons. In contrast, butter production decreased by 1.4% in 2024 [34].

An important indicator of progress toward the sustainable development goals of the Russian Federation is the level of moderate or acute food insecurity among the population, as measured by the scale of perceived food insecurity published by the Federal State Statistics Service every five years [35]. According to Table 2, acute

food insecurity in Russia has decreased; however, the issue persists due to economic difficulties that limit access to food, particularly for the most vulnerable groups.

Table 2

Moderate to Acute Food Insecurity

	2018	2023
Acute Food Insecurity (Food Insecurity Scale)	0.3	0.1
Moderate Food Insecurity (Food Insecurity Scale)	6.2	2.1

The level of moderate food insecurity in the Russian Federation is currently assessed as moderate. This assessment is supported by evidence that a portion of the population experiences difficulties in accessing food, many families' diets fail to meet recommended standards, and food inflation remains high.

DISCUSSION

The Russian dairy industry is developing slowly due to outdated technologies, worn-out equipment, a shortage of qualified personnel, and limited automation. Addressing these challenges requires substantial long-term investment. This conclusion aligns with the findings of S. K. Wegren et al., who note that although financial support for agriculture in nominal ruble terms continues to grow, the meat and dairy industries remain lagging in overall food production [36].

Local milk processors often provide financing to their suppliers, which places them at a disadvantage. Price disparities and resource limitations exacerbate this situation. Furthermore, there are no federal or regional instruments in place to adequately support milk producers.

In recent years, Russia's agricultural policy has shown signs of greater effectiveness. The Russian government actively monitors national food security, while regional authorities oversee agricultural development in their respective jurisdictions. Financial support for agro-industrial enterprises and targeted regional programs contribute to the growth of dairy production and the broader industry.

The Russian Food Security Doctrine identifies several ongoing risks for the agro-industrial complex [37]:

- Low investment attractiveness, technological lag, and insufficient innovative activity;

- Natural risks, including adverse weather conditions, which remain constant factors in agricultural forecasting.

To improve the agricultural sector, the Russian government has implemented measures such as:

- Active utilization of territorial resources;
- Attraction of investment;
- Modernization of equipment and introduction of advanced technologies.

However, A. Altukhov observes that current agricultural policies do not sufficiently address critical challenges, such as increasing enterprise profitability, enhancing product competitiveness, and promoting sustainable development in rural areas [38].

Ensuring access to food for the population is the most critical factor in improving the overall quality of life. Achieving this requires a comprehensive assessment of infrastructure across all stages, from production to final consumption.

Agriculture remains the foundation of the agro-industrial complex. It must supply the country with high-quality food and raw materials for industry. Strengthening the position of domestic producers necessitates increased investment and the adoption of innovative technologies, which will have a positive impact on the national economy.

Over the past ten years, Russia's agriculture has grown due to the integration of the agro-industrial complex and increased investment. An intervention grain fund has been established to stabilize the market and support prices. The quality of products in the market is regularly monitored, although the proportion of counterfeit products is declining slowly.

The sanctions imposed by developed countries have stimulated the development of the domestic agricultural industry through state support, thereby increasing production, exports, and food security for grains, poultry, pork, and eggs. Nevertheless, the material and technical base of agriculture remains outdated. A lack of funds hinders the adoption of new technologies, modernization of equipment, and reduction of production costs.

Agriculture faces challenges such as the deterioration of fixed assets and the continued use of outdated technologies. There is also an imbalance between the prices of industrial and agricultural goods. Additionally, Russian agriculture consumes more energy and resources compared to counterparts in the United States, Canada, and Europe, making it more costly and less efficient.

Food security depends on investment in the agricultural sector, rural development, and increased competitiveness of products. It is also essential to improve income policies and enhance the population's quality of life. Ensuring food security requires a combination of market self-regulation and targeted state support for the agro-industrial complex.

The sustainable development of Russia's agro-industrial complex is founded on the formation of clusters aligned with advanced technologies. An agrarian cluster is a composite structure that includes independent companies and is designed to support and develop agriculture. Within a cluster, companies that can succeed through collaboration play a crucial role. A cluster-based approach to cross-industry communication management fosters development for all participants.

This perspective aligns with the view of Academician A. I. Altukhov, who emphasizes the need for a unified strategy for the development of Russia's agro-industrial complex. Such a strategy would enable the identification of specialized zones for cultivating various agricultural products, optimize enterprise placement, promote the development of the food processing industry, and facilitate the formation of interregional and international clusters [38].

In the food industry, the problem of underutilized production capacities is particularly acute. Due to the sector's low investment attractiveness, the introduction of new technologies is challenging. Nevertheless, meat processing enterprises in Russia are being actively restored and modernized. Large integrated complexes are being developed that cover all stages of production, from grain cultivation to meat processing, allowing better control of the production process and ensuring high-quality products.

Russia aims to establish a competitive, export-oriented sector within the agro-industrial complex by 2025. Achieving this goal requires the adoption of modern technologies and the attraction of highly qualified specialists. Within the framework of the national project "*Development of Agriculture and Regulation of Agricultural Markets*", various measures are being implemented to support this objective.

The creation of modern processing enterprises is a complex task that necessitates coordinated efforts from both federal and regional authorities. It is also essential to enhance cooperation among participants in the processing industry. In 2017, a state program was approved to support agricultural development through the use of advanced technologies and to reduce dependence on foreign technologies [39].

A. Maslov and M. Avdeev emphasize the importance of actively introducing digital technologies in agriculture. Digitalization can increase labor productivity, accelerate industry modernization, and strengthen market positions of enterprises. It also reduces production and transaction costs, minimizes product losses, and optimizes production processes [40].

To enhance the competitiveness of agricultural products, it is necessary to optimize production and logistics processes, minimize losses at each stage, and actively invest in innovative technologies. It is noteworthy that approximately one-third of agri-food products are lost globally, while in Russia, losses exceed 40%.

CONCLUSION

The National Food Security Strategy should aim to:

1. Ensure the availability of food for all citizens.
2. Guarantee uninterrupted delivery of food to appropriate locations.
3. Maintain high quality and environmental safety of food products.
4. Support innovative agricultural production.
5. Promote integration along the chain “production – processing – sales”.
6. Reduce dependence on imports while supporting exports.

To achieve these objectives, it is necessary to:

1. Develop and approve national projects aimed at economic growth.
2. Optimize logistics for domestic manufacturers.
3. Establish evidence-based standards for healthy nutrition.
4. Support innovation within the food industry.

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The authors have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Gerardo Reyes Guzman. Universidad IEXE (Mexico)